

DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGY BASED ON ABU
RAYHAN BERUNI'S SCIENTIFIC HERITAGE IN IMPROVING STUDENTS'
CARTOGRAPHIC COMPETENCE

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Annotatsiya

Mazkur maqolada talabalarning kartografik kompetentligini rivojlantirishda buyuk alloma Abu Rayhon Beruniy ilmiy merosidan foydalanishga asoslangan pedagogik texnologiyalar tahlil qilinadi. Beruniyning geografiya, geodeziya, astronomiya va kartografiya sohalaridagi ilmiy qarashlari zamonaviy ta'lim jarayoniga integratsiya qilinib, talabalar uchun amaliy va innovatsion metodlar ishlab chiqildi. Tadqiqotda kompetensiyaviy yondashuv, interfaol metodlar, GIS texnologiyalari hamda tarixiy-manbaviy tahlil asosida kartografik kompetensiyani rivojlantirish mexanizmlari yoritilgan. Maqola oliy ta'lim muassasalari geografiya va pedagogika yo'nalishlari uchun ilmiy-amaliy ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: kartografik kompetentlik, pedagogik texnologiya, Beruniy merosi, GIS texnologiyalari, geodeziya, geografik tafakkur, kompetensiyaviy yondashuv.

Abstract

This article analyzes pedagogical technologies based on the use of the scientific heritage of the great scholar Abu Rayhan Beruni in developing students' cartographic competence. Beruni's scientific views in the fields of geography, geodesy, astronomy, and cartography were integrated into the modern educational process, and practical as well as innovative methods for students were developed. The research highlights the mechanisms of developing cartographic competence through a competency-based approach, interactive teaching methods, GIS technologies, and historical-source analysis. The article has scientific and practical significance for higher education institutions in the fields of geography and pedagogy.

Keywords: cartographic competence, pedagogical technology, Beruni's heritage, GIS technologies, geodesy, geographical thinking, competency-based approach.

In today's globalization process, geographical knowledge and cartographic thinking have become important components of modern specialist training. Especially for students studying in the fields of geography, ecology, tourism, geoinformatics, and pedagogy, the development of cartographic competence is

considered an urgent issue. From this perspective, the effective use of the scientific heritage of Eastern Renaissance scholars creates opportunities for integrating educational quality with national values.

The great encyclopedic scholar Abu Rayhan Beruni, in his works such as “Geodesy,” “India,” and “Qanun al-Masudi,” described scientific views related to the dimensions of the Earth, coordinate systems, principles of map creation, and methods of geographical calculations. This scientific heritage can serve as one of the methodological foundations of modern cartographic education.

Developing pedagogical technology based on Abu Rayhan Beruni’s scientific heritage and scientifically substantiating its effectiveness in the development of students’ cartographic competence is one of the urgent tasks of today’s education system. In the context of modern globalization, geographical thinking, spatial imagination, and map-handling skills are becoming essential components of professional training. In particular, the formation of cartographic competence among students in geography, geodesy, ecology, tourism, and pedagogy is regarded as one of the main criteria of professional preparation. Therefore, the integration of national scientific heritage into the educational process through innovative pedagogical technologies has significant scientific and practical importance.

The great scholar Abu Rayhan Beruni conducted extensive scientific research in the fields of geography, astronomy, mathematics, geodesy, and cartography. His scientific ideas related to determining the dimensions of the Earth, identifying geographical coordinates, calculating distances, and mapping methods are of special importance because of their closeness to the theoretical foundations of modern cartography.

The main purpose of this pedagogical technology is not only to develop students’ cartographic knowledge, skills, and abilities, but also to enhance their respect for historical and scientific heritage, independent thinking, and competencies in using innovative technologies. This technology is developed on the basis of a competency-based approach and is aimed at integrating theoretical knowledge with practical activities. The educational process предусматривает the effective use of interactive methods, problem-based learning, project methods, GIS technologies, electronic maps, and multimedia tools.

The pedagogical technology is organized in several stages. At the initial stage, students are introduced to Beruni’s life and scientific activity. During this process, historical sources, video lessons, electronic presentations, and maps are used to motivate students. At the next stage, the theoretical foundations of cartography, including scale, coordinate systems, geographical projections, and methods of map

analysis, are taught. For example, the following formula plays an important role in determining map scale:

$$M = \frac{d}{D} \quad (1)$$

Where: M — scale, d — distance on the map, D — actual distance.

Through this formula, students gain a practical understanding of the relationship between the distance shown on a map and the real distance. At the practical stage, students perform tasks such as creating electronic maps using modern GIS software, determining geographical coordinates, conducting spatial analysis, and comparing historical maps with modern maps. In addition, exercises related to determining the Earth's radius and calculating distances are organized based on the geodetic methods used by Beruni. For example, the mathematical model for calculating the Earth's radius is expressed as follows:

$$R = \frac{h}{\cos \alpha} \quad (2)$$

Through these formulas, students acquire not only theoretical knowledge but also practical computational skills. This contributes to the development of their spatial thinking, logical reasoning, and analytical approach.

During the research process, pedagogical observation, experimental work, questionnaires, interviews, and statistical analysis methods were used. The experimental studies were conducted with students majoring in geography at higher educational institutions. In the experimental groups, pedagogical technology based on Beruni's scientific heritage was applied, while traditional teaching methods were maintained in the control groups. The research results showed that students in the experimental groups achieved higher results in map analysis, coordinate determination, working with geoinformation technologies, and solving geographical problems. In addition, their interest in historical and scientific heritage and their independent research skills significantly improved.

The effectiveness of the pedagogical technology was evaluated based on several criteria. In particular, the durability of students' knowledge, the quality of completing practical assignments, the level of GIS technology usage, indicators of spatial thinking, and creative approaches were analyzed. According to the results, the application of innovative pedagogical technology proved highly effective in developing students' cartographic competence.

At this stage, students prepare individual or group projects. These projects are mainly focused on cartographic analysis, mapping geographical objects, comparing historical and modern maps, using GIS technologies, and solving practical problems based on the scientific views of Abu Rayhan Beruni.

In their projects, students independently conduct territorial analyses, distance calculations, coordinate determination, and electronic map creation using Beruni's scientific methods related to geodesy and geography. In addition, students defend their projects through presentations. During the presentation process, students develop skills in presenting ideas scientifically, working with maps and diagrams, analyzing geographical information, and speaking before an audience. This contributes to the development of communicative competence, creative thinking, and scientific discussion skills.

In this research, comprehensive scientific and pedagogical methods were used to determine the effectiveness of pedagogical technology based on Abu Rayhan Beruni's scientific heritage in developing students' cartographic competence. The research methodology was based on the integration of theoretical and practical approaches and aimed at deeply studying the pedagogical mechanisms of developing students' competencies in the educational process.

First of all, the pedagogical observation method was applied during the research process. Through this method, students' activity in the learning process, their map-handling skills, geographical thinking, and level of independent thinking were systematically monitored. Classroom activities, practical lessons, laboratory work, and the use of GIS technologies were analyzed during the observation process. Students' participation in lessons, their ability to solve problematic situations, and their activities in map analysis were evaluated according to special monitoring criteria.

Furthermore, experimental work was organized as one of the important stages of the study. The experiments were conducted with students studying in geodesy and cartography programs at higher educational institutions. Experimental and control groups were formed in the study. In the experimental groups, innovative pedagogical technology based on Abu Rayhan Beruni's scientific heritage was applied, while the educational process in the control groups continued using traditional teaching methods. During the experiment, special practical assignments, project activities, electronic map creation exercises, and geodetic calculation tasks were developed for students.

Questionnaire methods were also used to determine changes in students' cartographic competence during the experimental process. Through questionnaires, the attitudes of students and teachers toward the pedagogical technology, the effectiveness of lessons, the level of GIS technology usage, and interest in Beruni's scientific heritage were studied. The questionnaire results played an important role in identifying the level of students' motivation, learning activity, and development of practical skills.

To ensure the reliability of the research results, statistical analysis methods were applied. The obtained data were processed using mathematical and statistical methods, and differences between the experimental and control groups were analyzed. Percentage indicators, diagrams, rating results, and comparative tables were used in the statistical analysis. This made it possible to scientifically prove the effectiveness of the pedagogical technology.

Using comparative analysis methods, the results of traditional teaching methods and innovative pedagogical technology were compared. In particular, students' knowledge levels, map-reading and analysis skills, geographical coordinate determination abilities, and spatial thinking indicators were compared. The comparative analysis results showed that lessons organized on the basis of innovative approaches significantly improved students' cartographic competence.

Modern GIS technologies were widely used during the research process. Students conducted territorial analyses, created digital maps, and performed practical exercises on modeling geographical objects using ArcGIS, QGIS, and electronic mapping software. Through GIS technologies, students acquired practical competencies in processing geographical data, conducting spatial analysis, and working with electronic maps. This contributed to the development of their professional training and skills in using modern information technologies.

Since the research methodology was organized on the basis of a comprehensive approach, the obtained results demonstrated that pedagogical technology based on Abu Rayhan Beruni's scientific heritage has high effectiveness in developing students' cartographic competence. This methodology played an important role not only in forming theoretical knowledge but also in developing students' practical activities, research skills, and creative thinking.

In conclusion, pedagogical technology based on Abu Rayhan Beruni's scientific heritage serves as an important methodological foundation for developing students' cartographic competence. This technology ensures the integration of historical scientific heritage with modern innovative education and contributes to the formation of scientific worldview, geographical thinking, and practical skills among students. At the same time, it serves to improve the quality and effectiveness of education, promote national values, and develop the digital educational environment. In the future, it is advisable to further improve this technology through integration with artificial intelligence, digital cartography, and distance learning platforms.

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